

VOLTA: Multi-Terrain Humanoid Locomotion via Model Predictive Control (MPC) and Whole-Body Control (WBC)

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Abstract

The deployment of humanoid robots as assistants in healthcare and rehabilitative settings requires them to navigate human-centered environments—homes and hospitals—safely and reliably. However, the transition from structured laboratories to these complex, uneven terrains remains a fundamental challenge. Traditional position-controlled locomotion often lacks the compliance required for safe physical interaction and stability on soft surfaces, necessitating the adoption of torque-based control strategies to ensure the well-being of nearby humans.

This research introduces a humanoid locomotion framework designed to achieve robust walking for “VOLTA,” our custom-built kid-size humanoid robot (Figure 1b), through a hierarchical architecture combining Intrinsically Stable Model Predictive Control (IS-MPC) [1] and Passivity-based Whole-Body Control (PWBC) [2].

The proposed framework is structured into two levels (Figure 1a) to guarantee both planning feasibility and contact stability. The plan-level gait planner utilizes IS-MPC with a Linear Inverted Pendulum (LIP) model to generate optimal Center of Mass (CoM) trajectories that are appropriate for the desired robot velocities. IS-MPC incorporates a stability constraint linking the Zero Moment Point (ZMP) to the CoM state, guaranteeing internal stability (CoM of the robot will not diverge) even under disturbances. These references are tracked by the control-level PWBC, formulated as a Quadratic Programming (QP) problem using solver provided by Drake [3] and inverse dynamics, an equation that compute joints’ torque from Ground Reaction Forces (GRF). This layer optimally distributes task-space wrenches computed from the task impedance controller into GRF while satisfying friction cone and Center of Pressure constraints, ensuring the robot remains compliant yet balanced on unpredictable surfaces.

At the current stage, the research has established the foundational control architecture—defined as the integration of the PWBC with the hardware interface—and validated the system on the physical VOLTA robot, while the IS-MPC remains a focus for future implementation. In the Drake simulation environment [3], the PWBC has been successfully deployed, demonstrating capable static walking where the CoM is strictly regulated within the support polygon (Figure 1c). These simulation results confirm that the PWBC and inverse dynamics are functioning correctly to track both CoM and swing leg trajectories. On the physical VOLTA platform, significant milestones have been reached, including the full assembly of the 12-DOF lower body and the development of a custom motors’ torque control interface. The sensor system, comprising an encoder, a T265 camera for torso orientation and angular velocity along with foot-mounted force sensors, has been integrated to support state estimation. The fidelity of the PWBC has been validated through gravity compensation experiments, where the robot successfully maintained static balance against gravity without external support (Figure 1d), verifying the accuracy of the mass and inertia parameters essential for model-based control. The next phase of research will focus on integrating the IS-MPC to enable dynamic walking and transferring these controllers to hardware, allowing VOLTA to operate in real-world environments dynamically.

In summary, the control-level is functional on hardware (only gravity compensation) and successfully performs static walking in a simulation environment, setting the stage for the upcoming implementation of MPC-based dynamic walking.

References

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